

ERIC Forum Implementation Project

ERIC Forum Repository for Internal Communications

Work Package 5 - Deliverable 5.4

Deliverable no	D 5.4
Deliverable Title	ERIC Forum's repository for Internal Communications
Contractual delivery month	01.05.2019
Responsible Partner	
Author(s)	Salma Baghdadi, CERIC-ERIC

Copyright notice

This work by Parties of the ERIC Forum Implementation project Consortium is license under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Document log

Issue	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
D5.4	29-04-2019	ERIC Forum Repository for Internal Communication	Salma Baghdadi, CERIC-ERIC

Table of Contents

BACKGROUND	1
METHODS.....	4
SHAREPOINT.....	4
MAILING LISTS	4

1. Background

The internal communication among project partners is crucial for the smooth coordination within work packages and the efficient collaboration of the partnership.

The methods used to keep a continuous flow and exchange of information differs among project partners and the bodies. In addition to frequent email exchanges, the methods include the following:

- PMT (Project Management Team): monthly calls
- Work Packages: Calls among WP members and/or task leaders.

Moreover, the project's annual meeting is a crucial event to meet Face2Face and update the partnership about the situation of each WP.

It is important to set repository tools which would support in a better structuring and storage of information generated throughout the project. For this, the two major tools agreed-upon within the partnership are: SharePoint and the mailing lists.

2. Methods

1.1 SharePoint

The platform used for storing data, tracking deliverables' and editing documents is SharePoint. It is a collaborative management and storage platform which integrates Microsoft Office.

The main advantages of using SharePoint as the project's major repository are:

- The cost: SharePoint is included in BBMRI-ERIC Microsoft licenses, which allows the set-up of SharePoint folder to which we can invite as many contributors as needed, for no additional costs.
- It can be customised to the project's needs: via SharePoint, it is possible to create and share calendars, tasks' lists, distributions lists, forums/discussion boards and more.
- It can be used by various institutions' email: For organisation using Office365, the creation of an additional account is not needed. For others, it is possible to use personal emails/accounts.
- SharePoint can be fully integrated with Microsoft Windows computers. It also works well with Microsoft products as well as Apple ones.

The project's SharePoint repository is structured into two folders: one folder related to the Forum and a second one which feeds the project-related data and documents.

- *The Forum's folder*: it includes input from past and upcoming ERIC Forum meetings, such as the presentations, meeting agendas, and any document which would be relevant for the community.

- *The Project's folder*: It is organized as follow:

Folder name	Folder components
Contracts	Consortium agreements signed by each Partner, Grant Agreement, and other.
Deliverables	This folder is divided by WPs and incorporates the deliverables' final versions. Partners can include their feedback online directly on the related document.
SharePoint	This folder includes a guide to how to set-up and use SharePoint. It is applicable for various devices.
Meetings & Minutes	This folder includes documents of the project annual meetings (presentations, meeting minutes, logistics-related documents, registration and/or feedback forms, agenda, etc.) It also includes the output from the PMT meetings.
Publications	This folder includes the press releases and major publications of the ERIC Forum. It could include documents which are already existing in other folders, however, having it in the main folder makes it easily accessible for project partners.
Reports	This folder includes the main reports of WPs, such as the financial report.
WPs folders	Each WP has a separate folder so that related members can structure it according to their needs and preferred work-flow.

1.2 Mailing Lists

Taking into account the various project bodies and groups, the mailing lists are created to facilitate

the communication and make sure that all members of each certain group are aware and have the same information on a timely basis.

Each mailing list is created to meet different needs. The lists are categorized as follow:

- A list for each WP of the project, and it includes the project partners working on the specific WP. It will be managed by the respective WP leader.
- a list for the PMT (Project Management Team), which will be managed by the project coordinator.
- an email which will be available on the Forum's website and through which the public audience can interact with the community. It will be managed by WP5 Communication & Dissemination.
- a list for ERICs' directors, which will be managed by the project coordinator.